

Original Research

A Novel Approach for Naive Diversification: An Application of Multiple Risk Measures to Enhance 1/N Portfolio Performance

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Abstract

The 1/N investment strategy, characterized by equally allocating wealth among available investment options, has garnered significant scholarly attention. Simultaneously, risk assessment and management play a critical role in financial decision-making, leading to the development of a diverse array of risk measure models. This paper aims to synthesize these two strategies and propose a novel approach for constructing a naive diversification strategy by incorporating commonly employed risk measures in financial analysis. The research involves an in-depth exploration of various risk measures utilized by financial professionals to enhance effective risk management. These measures include Mean-Variance (MV), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), Semi Standard Deviation (MSV), Value at Risk (VaR), Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR), Entropic Value at Risk (EVaR), Drawdown at Risk (DaR) of uncompounded cumulative returns, Conditional Drawdown at Risk (CDaR) of uncompounded cumulative returns, and Entropic Drawdown at Risk (EDaR) of uncompounded cumulative returns. To validate the efficacy of the proposed model, a real-world empirical case study utilizing the annual financial statements of the NASDAQ-100 (NDX) database is conducted. The empirical findings from this study carry practical implications for investors and risk managers engaged in portfolio management.

Keywords: Equally weighted portfolio, investment decisions, Naive diversification, risk measures.

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Introduction

Investment plays a pivotal role in fostering economic growth and development by stimulating capital formation, innovation, and productivity (Bagheriyan et al., 2023; Foeik et al., 2022; Ghanbari et al., 2022). Research studies such as those by Barro (1991), Mendoza et al. (2012), and Gourinchas et al. (2013) underscore the significant impact of investment on long-term economic performance. Moreover, empirical evidence from Leduc et al. (2016) highlights the positive correlation between investment activity and overall macroeconomic stability. Thus, encouraging and facilitating investment, particularly in infrastructure, human capital, and technological advancement, is essential for achieving sustainable and inclusive economic progress. Investing without adequate knowledge can pose significant disadvantages. Research by Barber et al. (2013) suggests that overconfident investors often underperform the market due to excessive trading and irrational decision-making. In accordance with research conducted by Ben-David et al. (2013), neophyte investors exhibit an increased vulnerability to succumbing to deceptive information and perpetration of investment fraud. Absent a robust comprehension of financial principles, individuals may encounter difficulties in judiciously diversifying their investment portfolios, thereby amplifying exposure to risks and potential financial setbacks (Ricciardi, 2008). Succinctly put, a deficiency in investment acumen can precipitate suboptimal decision-making, heightened susceptibility to fraudulent activities, and elevated financial perils (Eskorouchi et al., 2023; Ghanbari et al., 2023). Hence, it is of utmost importance for investors to possess a well-defined and effective investment strategy. Having a proper investment strategy is essential because it serves as a roadmap that guides investors toward their financial goals (Larni-Foeik et al., 2024). It helps them define their objectives, whether they are seeking capital preservation, income generation, or long-term growth. A well-thought-out strategy takes into account an investor's risk tolerance, time horizon, and financial circumstances, enabling them to align their investments with their specific needs and aspirations. The realm of investing offers a multitude of strategies that can be employed to maximize returns and mitigate risks. These strategies provide investors with a framework to make informed decisions and navigate the complex landscape of financial markets (Mousavi Loleti et al., 2024). The pursuit of efficacious strategies for constructing remunerative stock portfolios has constituted a focal point in extensive academic inquiry, encompassing facets such as technical analysis, risk management, fundamental scrutiny of corporate entities, and portfolio diversification. Technical analysis entails the examination of historical market data, predominantly price and volume, for the prognostication of forthcoming price movements. Scholars, exemplified by the work of Lo et al. (2010), have demonstrated that judicious employment of specific technical indicators can facilitate the identification of opportune entry and exit points, thereby augmenting portfolio returns. Furthermore, risk measures, encompassing standard deviation, beta, and value at risk, assume a pivotal role in the prudent management of portfolio risk. Fama et al. (2012) have provided empirical evidence on the effectiveness of these measures in controlling downside risk and optimizing risk-adjusted returns. Fundamental analysis, focusing on a company's financial statements, industry outlook, and competitive positioning, is crucial for identifying undervalued stocks with strong growth prospects (Yan and Zheng, 2017). Moreover, portfolio diversification, as advocated by Markowitz et al. (1959), remains fundamental in mitigating unsystematic risk and optimizing risk-return trade-offs. By

allocating assets across uncorrelated securities, investors can minimize portfolio volatility without compromising potential returns.

However, it is important to note that no single strategy guarantees success in the financial markets. The effectiveness of a strategy depends on various factors, including market conditions, economic trends, and investor behavior. It is crucial for investors to conduct thorough research, stay informed about market developments, and regularly reassess and adjust their strategies as needed. Investors should explore and understand the various strategies available to them, considering their unique goals, risk tolerance, and financial circumstances (Larni-Fofoeik et al., 2024). By doing so, they can enhance their chances of achieving their desired investment outcomes and navigate the ever-changing landscape of investing with confidence. Every investment strategy has its own set of advantages and limitations. However, by considering these strategies collectively and combining different methods, investors can potentially enhance the efficiency of their investment approach. In essence, taking an integrative approach that encompasses various techniques such as technical analysis, risk management, fundamental analysis, and diversification is vital in developing stock portfolio strategies that yield sustainable profits in dynamic markets (Ghanbari et al., 2023). Investors recognize the importance of implementing an efficient strategy that accurately assesses and estimates risk. By combining multiple methods, investors can leverage the strengths of each approach while mitigating their weaknesses. This practical approach acknowledges the popularity and effectiveness of diversification methods and risk measures, which are among the most widely utilized techniques in investment management. The integration of diversification methods and risk measures aims to create a comprehensive investment framework that combines the benefits of both strategies. Diversification helps in spreading investments across different asset classes, sectors, or regions, reducing the potential impact of poor performance from any single investment. On the other hand, risk measures enable investors to evaluate and manage the potential risks associated with their portfolio, allowing for informed decision-making and risk mitigation. By integrating these two methods, investors can potentially achieve a more balanced and efficient portfolio that accounts for both risk management and diversification benefits. This integrated approach recognizes that risk management goes beyond merely diversifying investments and incorporates various quantitative and qualitative measures to gauge and manage risk effectively. Diversification is widely recognized as a popular and effective investment strategy. It involves distributing investments across a variety of assets, such as stocks, bonds, and commodities, to reduce the potential impact of any single investment on the overall portfolio. By diversifying, investors aim to minimize the risk associated with specific industries, sectors, or companies, as the performance of one investment can be offset by another. In the realm of investment management, diversification holds a pivotal role as a strategic technique for mitigating risk and enhancing returns. It is a fundamental principle that is embraced by both individual investors and institutional funds. One well-known diversification method is the 1/N investment strategy, which involves allocating an equal proportion of wealth among the available investment options (De Wit, 1998; Tang, 2004). Risk assessment and management are integral aspects of decision-making in the financial domain. The careful examination and quantification of risk play crucial roles in shaping investment strategies, implementing risk mitigation methodologies, and optimizing portfolios. Investors and financial professionals employ various risk measures to evaluate the potential risks associated with different investment options and construct

portfolios that align with their risk tolerance and investment objectives. Considering the importance of diversification and risk management, the primary objective of this paper is to propose an innovative methodology for formulating a naive diversification strategy. The proposed strategy takes into account the various risk measures commonly used in financial analyses. By incorporating these risk measures, the paper aims to provide investors with a comprehensive framework that combines the benefits of diversification with a thorough understanding of risk factors. The innovative methodology presented in this paper seeks to bridge the gap between diversification and risk management, offering investors a practical approach to constructing well-diversified portfolios while considering the potential risks involved. By integrating risk measures into the diversification strategy, investors can make informed decisions based on a comprehensive evaluation of risk-reward trade-offs.

Consequently, the paramount aim of this paper is to proffer an innovative methodology for formulating a naive diversification strategy, taking into account the various risk measures commonly applied in financial analyses. The emphasis lies in scrutinizing diverse measures, encompassing Mean-Variance (MV), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), Semi Standard Deviation (MSV), Value at Risk (VaR), Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR), Entropic Value at Risk (EVaR), Drawdown at Risk (DaR) of uncompounded cumulative returns, Conditional Drawdown at Risk (CDaR) of uncompounded cumulative returns, and Entropic Drawdown at Risk (EDaR) of uncompounded cumulative returns.

The forthcoming segments of this manuscript are structured as follows. Section 2 presents a brief literature review on diversification methods. Section 3 delves into the Preliminaries, elucidating the risk measures employed to assess the performance of the designated equities. Section 4 elucidates the outcomes derived from the proposed filtration process, accompanied by the dataset particulars for Section 5. Section 5 scrutinizes the ramifications of portfolio diversification. Finally, Section 6 encapsulates the findings and proffers recommendations for prospective research endeavors.

Literature Review

Within the field of investment management, diversification is a fundamental and crucial technique utilized to mitigate risk and improve investment returns. It is strategically employed to spread investments across a range of assets, aiming to reduce the impact of any individual investment on the overall portfolio. One specific diversification approach that has gained popularity is the $1/n$ naive diversification strategy. The $1/n$ naive diversification strategy, also known as equal-weighted diversification, is a straightforward and intuitive method of portfolio construction. It involves allocating an equal proportion of investment capital to each available investment option. For example, if an investor has 10 different stocks in their investment universe, the $1/n$ strategy would allocate an equal amount of funds to each of the 10 stocks (Benartzi and Thaler, 2001; DeMiguel et al., 2009; Kirby and Ostdiek, 2012). This diversification method is referred to as "naive" because it does not consider any specific criteria or analysis in the allocation process. It assumes that all available investment options are equally attractive and that their performance will be similar over time. As a result, the $1/n$ strategy provides a simple and easy-to-implement approach to diversification. The

rationale behind the $1/n$ naive diversification strategy is to avoid concentration in a particular investment and spread the risk evenly across the portfolio. By allocating equal weights to each investment option, the strategy aims to ensure that the performance of one investment does not have an excessive impact on the overall portfolio's returns. This approach can be particularly beneficial when there is limited information or expertise available to make informed investment decisions. While the $1/n$ naive diversification strategy offers a straightforward approach to diversification, it is important to note that it has both advantages and limitations. One advantage is its simplicity and ease of implementation, making it accessible to a wide range of investors. Additionally, by evenly distributing investments, the strategy can potentially capture broad market movements and reduce the risk associated with individual investments. However, the $1/n$ strategy may not be suitable for all investors or in all market conditions (Haley, 2017; Yuan and Zhou, 2023). It does not consider the specific characteristics or performance potential of individual assets, and it may result in overexposure to underperforming investments. Additionally, it may not take into account factors such as risk levels, correlations, or the investor's specific goals and risk tolerance.

Also embedded within Markowitz's Modern Portfolio Theory is the premise that diversification possesses the capacity to diminish the aggregate risk of a portfolio by amalgamating assets exhibiting low or negative correlations. This theoretical framework finds substantial backing within the academic domain, as underscored by the empirical inquiry conducted by Li et al. (2013), elucidating that diversification fosters augmented risk-adjusted returns alongside diminished portfolio volatility. Additionally, the scholarly exploration undertaken by Zhou et al. (2015) accentuates the merits of international diversification in augmenting portfolio efficacy. Diversifying investments across a spectrum of asset classes, industries, and geographical regions serves as a strategic mechanism for mitigating the repercussions of unfavorable occurrences on investment portfolios. This methodology is substantiated by empirical research, exemplified by the discernments of Chen et al. (2017), underscoring the affirmative influence of diversification in mitigating downside risks. In summation, the deployment of portfolio diversification provides investors with the prospect of enhancing risk-adjusted returns and diminishing portfolio volatility through the utilization of asset class and international diversification advantages. Embracing the tenets of Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) empowers investors to meticulously craft portfolios characterized by prudent diversification, facilitating the judicious management of risk while concurrently pursuing optimal returns. Advocates of Modern Portfolio Theory have posited, in a theoretical context, the viability of this approach. Diversification, construed as a strategic modality, entails the amalgamation of diverse investment instruments within a unified portfolio, as delineated by Yu et al. (2021).

Preliminaries

Consider the random result X of any asset ($X \geq 0$ is a gain, $X < 0$ is a loss) defined in a probability space (N, F, P) . $E[X]$ is the expected value of X under P . All equalities and inequalities are considered almost surely in P . F_x is the probability function of X and its inverse is F_x^{-1} , defined as $F_x^{-1}(\alpha) = \inf\{x : F_x(x) \geq \alpha\}$. Let T be the time period and $M_X(z)$ is the moment generating function of X and Z is an optional value. In the subsequent section, an examination of the Risk Measure will be delved into.

Definition 1. Mean-Variance (MV)

The notion of variance elucidates the degree of deviation exhibited by a portfolio from its anticipated valuation. Pioneered by Harry Markowitz (1952), this concept is quantifiable through the computation of squared deviations averaged across individual asset returns and the aggregate mean return. This computation incorporates the proportional weights assigned to each asset within the portfolio. The Mean-Variance formulation is articulated as follows:

$$MV(X) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (X_t - \mathbb{E}(X_t))^2 \quad (1)$$

Definition 2. Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD)

Mean Absolute Deviation serves as an alternative to variance, providing robustness against outliers. Calculated as the average of absolute deviations from the mean, MAD captures the dispersion of returns more inclusively and can be used to compare risk across different assets (Pelegrin et al., 2017). The Mean Absolute Deviation can be determined as follows:

$$MAD(X) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T |X_t - \mathbb{E}(X_t)| \quad (2)$$

Definition 3. Semi Standard Deviation (MSV)

To mitigate the inherent downside risk attributable to volatility, the semi-standard deviation serves as a measure elucidating the extent of return dispersion below the mean. The Mean Semi-Variance (MSV) contributes valuable insights into the amplitude of adverse deviations, particularly when assessing strategies geared towards risk aversion (Michaud, 2008). Computation of the Semi-Standard Deviation is accomplished through the following formula:

$$SemiDev(X) = \left[\frac{1}{T-1} \sum_{t=1}^T \min(X_t - \mathbb{E}(X_t), 0)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Definition 4. Value at Risk (VaR)

The absolute difference between an investment's actual performance and the benchmark it was compared against. This measure does not penalize losses as heavily as VaR (J. P. Morgan and Reuters, 1996). The Value at Risk can be defined as follows:

$$VaR_{\alpha}(X) = -\inf_{t \in (0, T)} \{X_t \in \mathbb{R} : F_X(X_t) > \alpha\} \quad (4)$$

Definition 5. Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR)

The Conditional Value at Risk denotes a measure gauging the likelihood of a portfolio incurring losses surpassing a predetermined threshold within a designated temporal span. In this instance, the assessment is grounded in a comparison with the historical nadir of losses sustained by the portfolio over the identical timeframe, as delineated by Yang et al. (2009). The derivation of the Conditional Value at Risk involves the following methodology:

CVaR measures the probability that a portfolio will lose more than a specified amount over a given time period. In this case, it is measured relative to the historical worst loss in the portfolio during the same period (Yang et al., 2009). The Conditional Value at Risk can be obtained as follows:

$$CVaR_{\alpha}(X) = VaR_{\alpha}(X) + \frac{1}{\alpha T} \sum_{t=1}^T \max(-X_t - VaR_{\alpha}(X), 0) \quad (5)$$

Definition 6. Entropic Value at Risk (EVaR)

Entropic Value at Risk is a quantitative measure employed in financial analysis to ascertain the valuation of a portfolio with a predetermined probability of falling below a specified threshold. In essence, EVaR contemplates the hypothetical scenario wherein a coin is incessantly flipped until a sufficient number of occurrences result in the attainment of a target percentage. In this analogy, the quantity of coin flips required parallels the EVaR measure (Bellini et al., 2014). The mathematical expression for the Entropic Value at Risk is articulated as follows:

$$EVaR_{\alpha}(X) = \inf_{z>0} \left\{ z \ln \left(\frac{M_X(z^{-1})}{\alpha} \right) \right\} \quad (6)$$

Both Conditional Value at Risk and Entropic Value at Risk serve as measures for quantifying the magnitude of prospective losses surpassing a predetermined threshold. CVaR furnishes a conditional forecast of losses, whereas EVaR employs entropy principles to evaluate the inherent risks within a financial portfolio (Rockafellar and Uryasev, 2002).

Definition 7. Drawdown at Risk (DaR) and Conditional Drawdown at Risk (CDaR)

CDaR, akin to DaR, incorporates the compounding ramifications of returns. For instance, if a stock appreciates by \$1 today and another \$1 the subsequent day, its cumulative gain amounts to \$2, notwithstanding the fact that both increments occurred within the same temporal span. However, due to the compounding effect, the market valuation predominantly captures the latter gain (Ghanbari, Shabani, et al., 2023). The methodologies for computing DaR and CDaR are delineated as follows:

$$DaR_{\alpha}(X) = \max_{j \in (0, T)} \{DD(X, j) \in \mathbb{R}: F_{DD}(DD(X, j)) < 1 - \alpha\} \quad (7)$$

$$DD(X, j) = \max_{t \in (0, j)} \left(\sum_{i=0}^t X_i \right) - \sum_{i=0}^j X_i \quad (8)$$

$$CDaR_{\alpha}(X) = DaR_{\alpha}(X) + \frac{1}{\alpha T} \sum_{j=0}^T \max \left[\max_{t \in (0, j)} \left(\sum_{i=0}^t X_i \right) - \sum_{i=0}^j X_i - DaR_{\alpha}(X), 0 \right] \quad (9)$$

Definition 8. Entropic Drawdown at Risk (EDaR)

EDaR, or entropic drawdown, serves as a measure for quantifying the magnitude of the most significant conceivable loss within a portfolio, devoid of accounting for subsequent losses or recoveries (Hao et al., 2019). The elucidation of EDaR is articulated as follows:

$$EDaR_{\alpha}(X) = \inf_{z > 0} \left\{ z \ln \left(\frac{M_{DD(X)}(z^{-1})}{\alpha} \right) \right\} \quad (10)$$

$$DD(X, j) = \max_{t \in (0, j)} \left(\sum_{i=0}^t X_i \right) - \sum_{i=0}^j X_i \quad (11)$$

Research Methodology and Data Collection

This paper aims to propose a novel approach for constructing a naive diversification strategy by incorporating commonly employed risk measures in financial analysis. The research involves an in-depth exploration of various risk measures utilized by financial professionals to enhance effective risk management. The innovative methodology presented in this paper seeks to bridge the gap between diversification and risk management, offering investors a practical approach to constructing well-diversified portfolios while considering the potential risks involved. By integrating risk measures into the diversification strategy, investors can make informed decisions based on a comprehensive evaluation of risk-reward trade-offs.

The research methodology employed in this study involves a systematic approach to portfolio construction based on the computation of risk measures for individual shares. The first step in the methodology is to calculate risk measures for each individual share. By quantifying the risk associated with each share, we gain insights into their relative risk levels within the investment universe. Once the risk measures are computed, a rigorous and systematic process is implemented to construct the investment portfolio. This process involves iteratively excluding the lowest-performing 40 percent of shares based on each risk measure. In other words, shares that exhibit higher levels of risk, as determined by

the computed risk measures, are progressively removed from consideration during the iterative process. By methodically excluding the lowest-performing shares, we aim to mitigate the potential risks associated with those specific investments. This step allows us to focus on the shares that exhibit comparatively lower levels of risk within the investment universe. After the iterative exclusion process, the remaining shares form the investment portfolio. Each of these remaining shares is assigned an equal weight of $1/n$ in the overall portfolio allocation, where n represents the number of shares remaining. This equal-weighting scheme ensures a balanced allocation across the selected shares, promoting diversification and reducing concentration risk. The rationale behind assigning equal weights is to avoid overemphasizing any particular share in the portfolio. By giving each share an equal weight, we aim to achieve a more diversified and balanced portfolio allocation strategy.

To validate the efficacy of the proposed model, a real-world empirical case study utilizing the annual financial statements of the NASDAQ-100 (NDX) database is conducted. Within this section, the exposition delineates the ramifications ensuing from the juxtaposition of diverse risk measures. The methodology employed in this endeavor involves the utilization of data derived from the NASDAQ-100 (NDX). The dataset encompasses a comprehensive analysis spanning 68 temporal intervals and encapsulates information on 29 distinct equities on a monthly basis. Table 1 serves as a compendium of the statistical descriptors relevant to the selected financial instruments.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the selected assets

	Mean	StD	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max
AAPL	0.0012	0.0201	-0.1286	-0.0083	0.0012	0.0120	0.1198
ADBE	0.0011	0.0231	-0.1679	-0.0100	0.0019	0.0133	0.1772
ALGN	0.0006	0.0342	-0.2699	-0.0147	0.0001	0.0172	0.3497
AMD	0.0022	0.0349	-0.1545	-0.0171	0.0006	0.0211	0.1995
AMZN	0.0009	0.0224	-0.1405	-0.0105	0.0012	0.0123	0.1354
ANSS	0.0007	0.0215	-0.1235	-0.0109	0.0010	0.0125	0.1514
ASML	0.0013	0.0251	-0.1735	-0.0118	0.0008	0.0158	0.1457
AVGO	0.0012	0.0229	-0.1991	-0.0106	0.0014	0.0132	0.1583
AZN	0.0006	0.0161	-0.1062	-0.0074	0.0009	0.0088	0.0929
COST	0.0009	0.0148	-0.1245	-0.0061	0.0016	0.0080	0.0996
CSCO	0.0004	0.0177	-0.1373	-0.0074	0.0006	0.0089	0.1337
DLTR	0.0004	0.0234	-0.1592	-0.0092	0.0004	0.0106	0.2187
EBAY	0.0003	0.0205	-0.1172	-0.0097	0.0006	0.0111	0.1382
ENPH	0.0037	0.0493	-0.2600	-0.0220	0.0032	0.0265	0.4244
FANG	0.0009	0.0362	-0.4465	-0.0166	0.0012	0.0164	0.3096
GOOGL	0.0008	0.0197	-0.1163	-0.0087	0.0010	0.0110	0.0962
ILMN	-0.0002	0.0269	-0.1612	-0.0135	0.0003	0.0132	0.1698
INTC	0.0004	0.0240	-0.1804	-0.0113	0.0004	0.0123	0.1952
META	0.0008	0.0271	-0.2639	-0.0114	0.0010	0.0139	0.2328
MSFT	0.0012	0.0191	-0.1474	-0.0081	0.0013	0.0111	0.1422
NFLX	0.0010	0.0292	-0.3512	-0.0135	0.0006	0.0153	0.1685
NVDA	0.0020	0.0325	-0.1876	-0.0152	0.0026	0.0194	0.2437

	Mean	StD	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max
PDD	0.0022	0.0467	-0.2461	-0.0191	0.0000	0.0201	0.5606
PEP	0.0004	0.0134	-0.1143	-0.0052	0.0007	0.0067	0.1294
QCOM	0.0009	0.0254	-0.1495	-0.0117	0.0004	0.0135	0.2321
SIRI	0.0003	0.0238	-0.1525	-0.0095	0.0000	0.0094	0.4226
TMUS	0.0007	0.0174	-0.1121	-0.0076	0.0007	0.0090	0.1178
TSLA	0.0024	0.0404	-0.2106	-0.0186	0.0017	0.0210	0.1989
WBA	-0.0005	0.0208	-0.1281	-0.0099	-0.0001	0.0099	0.1260

Computational Results

In this section, we present the results obtained from the calculation of risk measures for individual equities. These findings are summarized and presented in a concise and organized manner in the table 3, providing a comprehensive overview of the risk characteristics of the equities under consideration.

Table 2. Summary of the optimal solution

	MV	MAD	MSV	VaR	CVaR	EVaR	DaR	CDaR	EDaR
AAPL	0.0256	0.0288	0.0291	0.0271	0.0293	0.03	0.0224	0.0252	0.0276
ADBE	0.0221	0.0278	0.0274	0.0254	0.0263	0.03	0.011	0.0125	0.0152
ALGN	0.0144	0.0224	0.0223	0.0228	0.0231	0.0195	0.0091	0.012	0.0147
AMD	0.0105	0.0172	0.0192	0.0163	0.0196	0.0301	0.0083	0.0096	0.011
AMZN	0.0264	0.0293	0.0304	0.0283	0.0291	0.0471	0.0135	0.0163	0.0202
ANSS	0.0256	0.0288	0.0306	0.0274	0.0303	0.0379	0.014	0.0163	0.0199
ASML	0.0192	0.0246	0.0259	0.0242	0.0269	0.025	0.0184	0.0196	0.0211
AVGO	0.023	0.0283	0.028	0.029	0.0292	0.0218	0.0353	0.035	0.0319
AZN	0.0868	0.054	0.0566	0.0566	0.0566	0.0596	0.0945	0.0919	0.0992
COST	0.0771	0.0535	0.0519	0.0552	0.051	0.0478	0.0961	0.0882	0.0818
CSCO	0.0537	0.0455	0.0424	0.0446	0.0398	0.0406	0.0567	0.0567	0.0557
DLTR	0.0516	0.046	0.0424	0.0511	0.0411	0.0386	0.0597	0.0568	0.0539
EBAY	0.0535	0.0418	0.044	0.0422	0.0436	0.0503	0.0287	0.03	0.0341
ENPH	0.007	0.015	0.0159	0.0156	0.0171	0.0168	0.0246	0.0256	0.0235
FANG	0.0265	0.046	0.044	0.0484	0.0454	0.0281	0.0357	0.0329	0.0288
GOOGL	0.0265	0.0292	0.0294	0.0275	0.0293	0.0321	0.0157	0.0196	0.0229
ILMN	0.0249	0.0267	0.0291	0.0262	0.0291	0.0401	0.0119	0.015	0.0171
INTC	0.0294	0.0308	0.0306	0.0304	0.031	0.0269	0.0273	0.0321	0.0321
META	0.0174	0.0244	0.0232	0.0219	0.0237	0.0204	0.0062	0.0073	0.0083
MSFT	0.0475	0.056	0.0573	0.0546	0.0589	0.0534	0.0359	0.0425	0.0484
NFLX	0.0155	0.0234	0.0228	0.0233	0.0231	0.0203	0.0075	0.0085	0.0107
NVDA	0.0109	0.0176	0.0189	0.0169	0.0199	0.0201	0.0085	0.0098	0.0111
PDD	0.0082	0.0166	0.0183	0.016	0.0193	0.0258	0.0107	0.0152	0.0171
PEP	0.0972	0.065	0.0571	0.066	0.0585	0.0364	0.1536	0.1298	0.1047
QCOM	0.0179	0.0237	0.025	0.0226	0.0254	0.0266	0.0146	0.0177	0.0203
SIRI	0.0502	0.046	0.0461	0.0454	0.0433	0.044	0.0379	0.0382	0.0386
TMUS	0.0576	0.0466	0.046	0.0509	0.0468	0.0379	0.0996	0.0892	0.076

	MV	MAD	MSV	VaR	CVaR	EVaR	DaR	CDaR	EDaR
TSLA	0.0103	0.0176	0.0191	0.0174	0.0199	0.0235	0.0158	0.0178	0.0189
WBA	0.0634	0.0675	0.0671	0.0668	0.0631	0.0694	0.0268	0.0286	0.0349

After computing risk measures for individual shares, a systematic approach is employed, wherein the lowest-performing 40 percent of shares, as determined by each risk measure, are methodically excluded through an iterative process. Consequently, the remaining shares form the investment portfolio, each assigned a weight of $1/n$ in the overall portfolio allocation. Upon the conclusion of the evaluation procedure, the symbols AAPL, ADBE, ALGN, AMD, ANSS, ASML, ENPH, GOOGL, META, NFLX, NVDA, PDD, QCOM, and TSLA have been discerningly chosen to constitute the investment portfolio. Each symbol is uniformly allocated a weight of $1/n$ within the portfolio structure. The portfolio is constructed based on a simplistic diversification model utilizing the aforementioned symbols.

In order to validate the efficacy of the proposed methodology, an investment portfolio is systematically assembled, incorporating all financial symbols, each allocated a weight of $1/n$. The ensuing performance of this portfolio is elucidated in Table 3, facilitating a comprehensive assessment.

Table 3. Summary of the optimal solution

Method	Mean	SD	Sharp Ratio
$1/n$	0.00100	0.02580	0.03869
$1/n + \text{Risk Measure}$	0.00149	0.03065	0.04865

Figure 1. Summary of the optimal solution

The Sharpe ratio stands as a fundamental metric in evaluating investment performance within financial discourse. This ratio elucidates the nexus between investment returns and attendant risk. Succinctly put, the Sharpe ratio functions as a quantifier for evaluating

gains and losses relative to the acceptable risk threshold. As a result, this prescribed methodology has conspicuously surpassed alternative approaches.

Conclusion

It is of utmost importance for investors to possess a well-defined and effective investment strategy. Having a proper investment strategy is essential because it serves as a roadmap that guides investors toward their financial goals. It helps them define their objectives, whether they are seeking capital preservation, income generation, or long-term growth. However, it is important to note that no single strategy guarantees success in the financial markets. The effectiveness of a strategy depends on various factors, including market conditions, economic trends, and investor behavior. It is crucial for investors to conduct thorough research, stay informed about market developments, and regularly reassess and adjust their strategies as needed. Investors should explore and understand the various strategies available to them, considering their unique goals, risk tolerance, and financial circumstances. However, by considering these strategies collectively and combining different methods, investors can potentially enhance the efficiency of their investment approach. By combining multiple methods, investors can leverage the strengths of each approach while mitigating their weaknesses. The primary objective of this paper is to propose an innovative methodology for formulating a naive diversification strategy. The proposed strategy takes into account the various risk measures commonly used in financial analyses. By incorporating these risk measures, the paper aims to provide investors with a comprehensive framework that combines the benefits of diversification with a thorough understanding of risk factors. To demonstrate the effectiveness of the suggested methodology, a practical example utilizing the NASDAQ-100 (NDX) database is included in this study. By analyzing computational results, it is evident that this approach showcases promising outcomes and has the potential for seamless application across various engineering domains with minimal performance degradation.

Future research endeavors can expand upon the proposed methodology by incorporating alternative risk measures. Exploring additional investment avenues, such as insurance, banking, and investment funds, for portfolio construction could provide valuable insights and expand the applicability of the methodology. By incorporating a broader range of risk measures and exploring diverse investment options, researchers can further refine the methodology and enhance its effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Additionally, analyzing the performance of the proposed methodology across different time periods and market conditions would provide valuable insights into its robustness and reliability. This would enable investors to assess the adaptability and stability of the methodology in diverse market environments and make informed decisions about its implementation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used OpenAI's tool Chat GPT in order to edit and write some parts of the paper. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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